

Science Anxiety as a Function of Gender and Attitude in the Performance of Secondary School Biology in Bungoma County, Kenya

Kennedy W. Nyongesa¹

¹Department of Agriculture and Environmental Studies, The Eldoret National Polytechnic

Corresponding author's Email: kennyongesa@yahoo.com

Submission Date: Oct 3, 2024; **Revised Submission:** May 15, 2025; **Publication Date:** July 13, 2025

ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study was to investigate the influence of science anxiety on the performance of students in Biology. Science anxiety is a product of low self-efficacy. Science anxiety may contribute to students, particularly females, having low enrollment in science classes. Science anxiety emerges early in a student's exposure to the science curriculum. Various reasons can contribute to the feelings of science anxiety among teachers. This may, in turn, affect their teaching approaches and the methodology they frequently use. The teaching approaches and how the professional skills of the teacher are displayed may be dependent on the level of science anxiety the biology teacher has. It is a product of low self-efficacy. Some research on science anxiety supports the Social Cognitive Theory. Self-efficacy is the major construct emerging from this theory. The secondary school students' performance in Biology in the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) in Bungoma County has been steadily low. Nine (9) secondary schools were randomly selected for the study out of 139 schools in Bungoma County. Three hundred and sixty (360) form three students were randomly selected for the study. Questionnaires were used as instruments for data collection. Science anxiety was measured by the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), which has three Likert scales: Confidence Scale, Anxiety Scale, and the Interest Scale. Attitude was measured by the Attitude Inventory, which also has Likert Scale questions. Class Mark lists were used to measure the performance of students from Form 1 to Form 3 at the time of the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study established that boys perform better than girls in Biology. The study found that boys had a relatively more positive attitude toward Biology than girls. Girls were found to have a higher level of science anxiety in Biology compared to boys. The study, however, concludes that the gap has been narrowing sharply over the years. The findings of the study shall be of fundamental importance to policymakers and educationists regarding Biology education in particular and Science education in general.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, Science Anxiety; Attitude; Biology; Learner Factors; Performance

INTRODUCTION

Stephen Doh Fia et al (2022) posit that anxiety toward science might be subject-specific. Furthermore, in studies of science anxiety as a function of gender, the results showed that although there were no gender differences in terms of science test performance, girls reported consistently higher levels of anxiety, both in terms of general and subject-specific science (Shibli, 2015). Earlier findings indicated a wider gap. The differences in the levels of science anxiety between the male and female students have, however, been narrowing over the years (Nyongesa, 2011).

Barrera (2016) concluded that Science anxiety as a function of attitude means that a person's level of anxiety towards science is directly influenced by their overall attitude and perception of the subject, with negative attitudes often leading to higher levels of science anxiety; essentially, the more negative someone feels about science, the more anxious they are likely to be when encountering scientific concepts or tasks.

Bandura (1997) developed the Social Cognitive Theory from programmed research on social development. The Social Cognitive Theory suggests that anxiety is a result of feelings of inefficacy; anxiety then leads to avoidance of situations that arouse the feelings of inefficacy. Self-efficacy is a cognitive processing mechanism that guides human action. It is one's perceived performance capabilities. This perceived performance capability affects behavior and attitude (Ghani-Hamzah, 2019)

Providing evidence of this relationship, some teachers reported in informal interviews that they did not teach much science because they were not very good at it, they taught science only because they had to and hence, they did it in a perfunctory manner, when possible, they traded this responsibility with someone who was better prepared (Horton & Hutchinson, 1997). The authors observed that, by impression, although these teachers felt powerless to positively affect their students' science learning, it was not very surprising. One has to believe that one's attitude can bring about a desired outcome if one is to execute the behavior required to achieve that outcome (Kuhr, 2003; Ghani-Hamzah, 2019).

Science anxiety is correlated with science achievement, and it is gender-related (Nyongesa, Nyongesa, Musima & Kiboss, 2016). Gorell and Capron (1990) suggested that without a belief in their ability to affect students' performance, teachers do not accept responsibility for motivating students' learning. There is a suggested relationship between teacher self-efficacy, teacher performance, and student achievement (Nyongesa, 2011). High levels of teacher self-efficacy have been associated with greater student achievement and greater teacher commitment to student achievement as well as higher expectations for children (Ashton, Webb & Doda, 1983). A high level of anxiety accompanies poor student performance in most academic areas, and highly anxious students tend to lack self-confidence, curiosity, and adventurousness (Westerback, 1984). People gather information about their self-efficacy in various ways (Czerniak, 1992). Social influences such as positive reinforcement and verbal persuasion contribute to perceived capabilities, and the strongest factor affecting self-efficacy is actual performance attainment (Stephen Doh Fia et al.,2022).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Science anxiety is a product of low self-efficacy (Yager & Penick, 1985; Zakariya, 2022). Science anxiety may contribute to students, particularly females, having low enrollment in science classes. Science anxiety emerges early in a student's exposure to the science curriculum. Various reasons can contribute to the feelings of science anxiety among the

teachers (Czerniak, 1992; Ghani-Hamzah, 2022). This may, in turn, affect their teaching approaches and the methodology frequently used. The teaching approaches and how the professional skills of the teacher are displayed may be dependent on the level of science anxiety the biology teacher has (Nyongesa, 2011). The author posits that female teachers were found to have a higher level of science anxiety in the teaching of Biology compared to male teachers. However, this does not mean that female teachers are inferior or incompetent compared to male teachers. The study concludes that Science anxiety has been related to the teachers' performance in science teaching. Highly anxious teachers tend to lack self-confidence, curiosity, and creativity in their teaching approaches (Spielberger & Syderman, 1994). This is likely to have noticeable effects on both the quantity and quality of science instruction that may negatively impact the student's attitude and anxiety towards the subject (Westerback, 1984). Thus, teachers' anxiety over teaching science is likely to have profound effects on science instruction that may negatively affect students' attitudes toward the subjects (Westerback & Long, 1990; Nyongesa, 2011). This kind of teacher is likely to develop a negative attitude towards the students and his/her interaction with the students will be negative and this may contribute to a negative attitude of the students towards Biology with the likelihood of the students developing high levels of anxiety towards the subject (Stephen Doh Fia et al., 2022).

For students who are enrolled in science classes, an increase in anxiety may result in lowered achievement (Spielberger & Syderman, 1994). Lawrenz and Cohen (1985) found that students gave "difficulty" as a reason for not enrolling in science classes. Westerback (1982) found that anxiety increased with the increased complexity and difficulty of learning tasks. Teachers who provided clear expectations, opportunities for remedial instruction, and study support reduced anxiety toward science in the students. This supports earlier research by Bandura (1977) in which students were less anxious in courses where they learned material in smaller chunks, received feedback, and had opportunities to master concepts before proceeding with further learning; this tended to improve their positive attitudes towards the subject matter. Ghani-Hamzah (2019) posits that students generally exhibit higher levels of science anxiety in STEM subjects. According to the SMASE Project (2000; Nyongesa et al, 2016a), Biology as a science subject requires an integration of both theoretical and practical work for the students. This, therefore, calls for the application of a myriad of teaching aids to enable learners to concretize biological principles, concepts, and facts. The teacher of Biology, thus, must apply the student-centered approach (Stephen Doh Fia et al., 2022).

Experiences with management and control of science classes, which differ in some other subject areas due to the laboratory, inquiry-based nature of science, should be an integral part of teacher education courses (Ashton, Webb & Doda, 1983; Nyongesa, Singoro, Kiboss, Mbugua & Njuguna, 2014). The work of King and Wiseman (2001) lends leverage to this observation. Students as early as the third-grade exhibit anxiety towards science, and students' interest in science starts declining between the third and seventh grades (Horton & Hutchinson, 1997). Students' self-efficacy judgments influence performance and aspirations, including career goals, and persistence at a task is enhanced when one believes in his/her ability to continue the task despite the obstacles. For example, if one perceives oneself as incapable of comprehending science or mathematics and fails to persist in learning science and mathematics, it is unlikely one will elect a career in medicine, technology, or other science/math-related areas. Students' performance expectations influence their persistence at tasks, their achievement, and their aspirations (Bandura, 1986; Ghani-Hamzah, 2022).

Students' self-efficacy seems to affect their ability to learn science. Students are likely to become anxious about science after repeated bad experiences, such as poor science instruction,

few role models, especially for females; personal failure in science, and negative attitudes of adults and peers (Westerback, 1984). Once students have had repeated bad experiences with science, their perceptions of themselves are affected negatively; this leads to inferior images of their self-concept and results in anxiety and negative attitudes toward science (Nyongesa et al, 2016). Bandura (1997) reported that increased self-efficacy and decreased anxiety could be achieved through modeling, by watching other females succeed in science, being exposed to females in science careers, or observing competent female teachers of science, girls may elect to take more science-related careers. Integrating science into other settings and subject areas seems to have a particularly positive effect on females (Carlson and Buskist, 1997). Females favored the social problems approach to teaching and learning science more than males (Hong, Woo & Jeong, 1995; Zander, 2020). Nyongesa (2015) observed that females might learn science more effectively if scientific and technological concepts were integrated into the curriculum, and finally, instruction that emphasizes lowering anxiety about science for females (Nyongesa et al., 2014b; Zander, 2020).

Conceptual Framework

The Conceptual framework used in this study is based on the Systems Theory presented by Joyce and Weil (1980). The General Systems Theory is derived from the systems concept (Mukasa-Simiyu, 2001). The systems concept emphasizes a method of looking at wholes and attempting to establish the relationship among the parts. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of this study.

Figure 1: Relationship between learner factors and performance and moderated by home, school, and teacher factors
Source: Nyongesa, 2011

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Biology has a lot of relevance in everyday life because it helps people understand themselves and the environment, especially with the advent of anthropogenic climate change. This can positively affect sustainable development and adaptive resource management. Students and teachers towards learning and teaching science subjects exhibit Science anxiety. Biology plays a key role in environmental conservation, which today inclines a lot towards climate change mitigation and adaptation, and other sectors of the economy.

METHODOLOGY

Two research designs were used, namely, the Cross-Sectional survey design and the Ex post facto design. This was necessary to obtain triangulation of information from the data collected. The Cross-Sectional survey design was typical for this study because the design was working

to find out the occurrence, relationships, and distributions of gender, attitude, and science anxiety of the learners and how these factors influence the performance of the students in Biology. The Ex post facto design was used to gather information on the performance of the students in Biology. In this design, research is done on what has already happened, according to Bartlett, Kotrlik, and Higgins (2008). The Ex post facto design, also called the Causal Comparative Research, is useful when two groups are involved and they show differences in dependent or independent variables (Ader, Mellenbergh, and Hand, 2008). A study of the differences becomes necessary.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The mean attitude scores for students of both genders are presented in Table 1 below. Attitude values were obtained from the Attitude Inventory.

Table 1: Mean Scores of Attitude Levels for Students of both genders

Variable: Attitude	Gender	
Questions: Strongly disagree - strongly agree (1-2-3-4-5)	M (N=162) Mean-score	F (N=168) Mean-score
Biology is easy to understand	3.5	3.2
Biology leads to good careers	3.2	3.4
Biology should be made compulsory	3.2	3.1
I would take Biology at a higher level of my education	4.5	3.6
I enjoy learning Biology	4.8	3.2

Information in Table 1 reveals that male students have a higher attitude score (19.2/25) as compared to the female students (15.5/25) in the learning of Biology.

Science Anxiety Levels of Students towards Biology

The students responded to the State Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), which measured their levels of science anxiety towards Biology. The STAI was developed by Westerback (1984) and adopted by Czerniak (1992), Spielberger and Syderman (1994), and later adopted by Nyongesa (2011) in this study. The STAI has three scales, namely, the anxiety scale, confidence scale, and interest scale. Table 2 below carries information that shows the mean scores on each scale. The total of the mean scores gave the level of science anxiety for both the male and female students.

Table 2: Mean Scores of Science Anxiety Levels for Students of both Genders

Variable	Gender	Mean
Anxiety Scale	M	3.8
At ease - Anxiety (1-2-3-4-5-6-7)	F	3.6
Confidence Scale	M	2.9
Confidence - Fear (1-2-3-4-5-6-7)	F	2.9
Interest Scale	M	2.4
Curious – Uninterested (1-2-3-4-5-6-7)	F	3.1
Total Mean Score	M	9.1
	F	9.6

Information in Table 2 shows that male students have lower levels of science anxiety (9.1) in Biology as compared to the female students, with a higher level of science anxiety (9.6). Nevertheless, the gap seems to be narrowing (Nyongesa, 2011) when compared to the findings of Westerback (1984) and Czerniak (1989).

Causes of Anxiety towards Learning Biology

Table 3 shows the distribution of the student sample according to the main cause of anxiety towards learning Biology as related to their gender.

Table 3: Causes of Anxiety towards Learning Biology

Main Cause	Gender (Male)	%	Gender (Female)	%
Increasing complexity of the subject	17	10.7	35	18.4
Lack of teacher role models of the same gender	16	9.5	50	26.5
Lack of remedial teaching and consultation	34	20.2	16	8.2
The teaching is very fast, giving no room for mastery of concepts	17	10.1	16	8.2
The teacher always wants the right answers when questioning	16	9.5	19	10.1
Inadequate practical lessons	34	20.2	28	14.3
Long congested syllabus	34	20.2	28	14.3
Total	168	100.0	192	100.0

Information in Table 3 indicates that most female students (26.5%) developed anxiety towards the learning of Biology because of a lack of teacher role models of the same gender. This serves the fact that most of the biology teachers are male. Twenty-eight (14.3%) of the female students held the view that a lack of adequate practical lessons could contribute towards anxiety, and another twenty-eight (14.3%) female students believed that a long-congested syllabus was their main cause of anxiety. More female students (10.1%) as compared to the male students (9.5%) developed anxiety towards the subject when the teacher always expected right answers from them when questioning in class. A large percentage of male students (60.6%) developed

anxiety because of three main causes, namely, lack of remedial teaching and consultation, lack of adequate practical lessons, and a long and congested syllabus.

Students' Performance in Biology

Figure 2 shows the indicates that boys had an overall better performance than the girls in Biology since joining form one (1) to three (3), regardless of their gender.

Figure 2: Boys had an Overall better performance than the girls in Biology.

Figure 3: Boys had a General Higher Average performance than the girls in Biology.

Information in Figure 2. Category 4 indicates the performance score between grade B, B+ to A while category 3 indicates the performance score between grade C, C+ to B- while category 2 indicates the performance score between grade D, D+ to C-; category 1 indicates the performance score between grade E to D; thus, from Figures 2 and 3, it implies that Biology is among the gender-related subjects. Information in Figure 3 indicates that boys had a generally higher average performance than the girls in Biology

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study indicate that girls have a higher level of science anxiety than boys do. This finding is similar to that of those who found that females, as early as the third grade, exhibit more anxiety than their male counterparts. This anxiety may contribute to the students, particularly females,' low enrollment in science classes. The study found that some girls developed science anxiety because of a lack of teacher role models of the same gender. There was a general shortage of female teachers, and male teachers dominated in most schools. Even though role modeling through female teachers has proved quite effective in some single – gender secondary schools in Kenya, where some girls' schools have tended to outperform some boys' schools in science and mathematics, very few co-educational schools can boast of such an advantage.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the teachers of Biology must consider the emotional, social, and intellectual constructs if we are to examine the total educational goal of schools. SMASE- ASEI/PDSI is a model that guides teacher professional development activities, which allow teachers to think and reflect on ways to ensure that learners are at the centre of the teaching and learning process. The school should stimulate the kind of participation that gives positive support to the learning of Biology, such as the supply of teaching-learning aids. These instructional materials should be free of gender biases and stereotypes. The knowledge, the intelligence, and academic excellence the teachers possess have a direct bearing on the quality of education provided by schools (UNESCO, 1991; Orodho, 1996; Stephen Doh Fia et al., 2022). Role models are important for effective science teaching, especially for elementary teachers (Bandura, 1997). This can effectively take care of the attitudes and science anxiety of the students in the learning of Biology concerning gender. From the findings of this study, it can be concluded that boys perform relatively better than girls in Biology because they have a relatively more positive attitude than girls, and relatively lower levels of science anxiety as compared to girls. Role models, especially in the field setting, greatly influence teachers. Evans and Tribble (1986) concluded that role models such as cooperating teachers, influence pre-service teachers more than theoretical preparation on campuses. The structure of administrative organization in schools can affect teachers' sense of efficacy, which in turn affects the attitude levels of learners (Aston, 1984; Zander, 2020). Finally, it can be concluded that the students' gender, attitude, and science anxiety, and their influence on performance in Biology, are inseparable and must be addressed collectively. Their relationship can be illustrated in the model shown below. Figure 3 shows the conclusive working model illustrating the inter-relationship between science anxiety, gender, attitude, and performance in Biology as envisaged by this study.

Figure 3: The Conclusive Working Model: Relationship between Students' Science Anxiety, Gender, Attitude, and Performance in Biology.

Source: Nyongesa, 2011

RECOMMENDATIONS

Some recommendations are listed below without elaboration at this point.

1. Gender-sensitive methodologies should be incorporated in the pre-service and in-service training programs.
2. Teachers should promote gender equity and equality in education and training from a life cycle approach.
3. Some students may need motivational guidance and counseling, which may partially eliminate the negative effects of the non-science environment at home.
4. Biology instruction in class must be based on the positive elements of the characteristics and expectations of the students.
5. Teachers of Biology should embrace the ASEI/PDSI approach as advanced by the SMASE Project and minimize the science anxiety of the learners because of the many hands-on activities involved in the approach.

REFERENCES

- Ashton, P. (1984). Teacher efficacy: A motivational paradigm for effective teacher education. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 35(5), 28-32.
- Ader, H. J.; Mellenbergh, G.J.& Hand, D. J. (2008). *Advising on research methods: A Consultant's companion*. Huizen, The Netherlands: Johannes van Kessel Publishing.
- Ashton, P., Webb, R. & Doda, N. (1983). *A study of teachers' sense of self-efficacy: Final Report* (Vol. Gainesville, F.L: University of Florida. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 231 834).
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioural change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191-215.
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social Foundations of thought and action*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Barrera, T. L., Szafranski, D. D., Ratcliff, C. G., Garnaat, S. L., & Norton, P. J. (2016). An experimental comparison of techniques: Cognitive diffusion, cognitive restructuring,

- and in vivo exposure for social anxiety. *Behavioural and Cognitive Psychotherapy*, 44(2), 249-254.
- Bartlett, J. E, II; Kotrlik, J. W. & Higgins, C. (2001). Organizational research: Determining appropriate sample size for survey research. *Information technology, Learning and Performance Journal*, 19(1) 43-50.
- Carlson, N.R. & Buskist, W. (1997). *Psychology: The Science of Behaviour*. Boston: Allyn Bacon.
- Czerniak, C. M. (1992). *A qualitative comparison of elementary pre-service teachers identified as high and low anxiety about teaching Science*. National Association of Research in Science Teaching, Boston, M.A.
- Czerniak, C.M. (1989). *An investigation of the relationships among science teaching anxiety, self-efficacy, teacher education variables, and instructional strategies*. Dissertation Abstract International.
- Evans, E. & Tribble, M. (1986). Perceived teaching problems, self-efficacy, and commitment to teaching among pre-service teachers. *Journal of Educational Research*, 80, 81-85.
- Fia, S. D., Fosu-Ayarkwah, C., & Obuobi-Ayim, T. (2022). Causes, Effects, and Management of Science Anxiety among Senior High School Students in Old Tafo Municipality of Ghana. *Open Journal of Psychology*, 2(1), 46–57.
- Horton, R.L. & Hutchinson, S. (1997). *Nurturing scientific literacy among youth through experientially based curriculum materials*. National Network for Science and Technology, Julie Chaplin, 6H Berkley Hall, Michigan State University, E-Lansing MI 28824.
- Gorell, J. & Capron, E. (1990). Cognitive modeling and self-efficacy: Effects on pre-service teachers' learning of teaching strategies. *Journal of Teacher Education*.
- Ghani-Hamzah, M. S., Motevalli, S., & Garmjani, M. G. (2019). Effects of cognitive restructuring and study skills training on anxiety and academic achievement. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4(17), 248-258.
- Hong, S., Woo, J., & Jeong, J. (1995). An analysis of proceedings on science teacher and science teacher education in Korea and America. *Journal of Korean Association for Research in Science Education*, 15(3)241-249.
- Joyce, B. & Weil, M. (1980). *Models of teaching*. New Jersey, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- King, K., & Wiseman, D.L. (2001). Comparing science efficacy beliefs of elementary education majors in integrated and non-integrated teacher education coursework. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 12(2), 143-1.
- Kuhr, J. (2003). *Teacher-directed school reform movements: The use of improvisational theater for social change in the classroom*. Unpublished honors thesis, University of Massachusetts, Amherst, MA.
- Lawrenz, F., & Cohen, H. (1985). The effects of methods, classes, and practical teaching on students' attitudes towards science and knowledge of science. *Science Education*, 69, 105-113.
- Mukasa-Simiyu, A. (2001). *The Systems Approach to Teaching: A Handbook for Teachers*. Eldoret: Western Educational Publishers.
- Nyongesa, K.W. (2011). *Influence of Gender, Attitude, and Science Anxiety on Performance of Secondary School Students in Biology in Bungoma District, Kenya*. Published M.Ed. (Sc) Thesis. Egerton University-Njoro, Kenya.
- Nyongesa, K.W. Singoro B. W, Kiboss J. K, Mbugua Z. K & Njuguna J. (2014). Curriculum Integration for Knowledge Management: A Prospective Concept. *The Cradle of Knowledge African Journal of Education and Social Science Research*, Vol. 2(1), 2014 ISSN 2304-2885.

- Nyongesa, K.W. (2015). A Teacher's Perspective on the Challenges in the Delivery of Content and Performance in Biology: A Case of Bungoma District, Kenya. *Kabarak Journal of Research Innovation*. Vol.3(2), pp. 23-42. <http://eserver.kabarak.ac.ke/ojs/>.
- Nyongesa K. W.; Nyongesa M.S.; Musima C; & Kiboss, J., (2016a). A Review of Factors that Influence Performance of Students in Science Subjects at Secondary School Level with a Focus on Kenya: Is there a Disconnect? *The Cradle of Knowledge: African Journal of Educational and Social Science*. Vol. 3(1).
- Nyongesa K.W.; Mbotela Khisa & Maende, C.M., (2016b). Science Education in Kenya Secondary Schools: A Gender Profile of Students in Bungoma District. *Journal of Technology & Socio-Economic Development*.
- Orodho, A. J. (1996). *Factors influencing students' performance in science subjects Secondary school level in Kenya*. Unpublished PhD thesis, Kenyatta University.
- Shibli, N. (2015). The effects of anxiety on achievement and performance: A college study. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 5(6), 1-2.
- SMASSE project. (2000). *Resources and Facilities for Teaching and Learning Biology*. Nairobi: MOEST-JICA.
- Spielberger, C.D. & Syderman, S. (1994). *Strait-Trait Anxiety Inventory and Strait Trait Anger Expression Invention*. In M.E. Maruish (Ed.), *The use of psychological tests for treatment planning and outcome assessment* (pp. 292-321). Hillsdale, NJ: LEA.
- Twoli, N.W. (1986). *Sex Differences in Science Achievement among Secondary School Students in Kenya*; Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, Flinders. University of Australia.
- UNESCO (1991). *World Education Report*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Westerback, M.E. (1982). Studies on attitude towards teaching science and anxiety about teaching science in pre-service elementary teachers. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*. 21, (9),937-950.
- Westerback, M.E. (1984). Studies on anxiety about teaching science in pre-service elementary teachers. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 21, (9)937-950.
- Westerback, M.E. & Long, M.E. (1990). Science knowledge and the reduction of anxiety about teaching earth science in elementary teachers as measured by the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory. *School Science and Mathematics*, 90(5).
- Yager, R.E., & Penick, J.E. (1985). *Science teacher education*. In W.R. Houston (Ed.), *Handbook of research on teacher education*.
- Zakariya, Y. F. (2022). Improving students' mathematics self-efficacy: A systematic review of intervention studies. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13,986622.
- Zander, L., Hohne, E., Harms, S., Pfof, M., & Hornsey, M. J. (2020). When grades are high but self-efficacy is low: unpacking the confidence gap between girls and boys in mathematics. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 552355.